

A STATISTICAL FRAMEWORK FOR ECONOMIC APPLICATIONS OF DOUBLE MULTIVARIATE EXPONENTIALLY WEIGHTED MOVING AVERAGE (DMEWMA) CONTROL CHARTS

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ABSTRACT

This paper proposes an Economic Statistical Design of the Double Multivariate Exponentially Weighted Moving Average (DMEWMA) control chart and compares it with the Multivariate Exponentially Weighted Moving Average (MEWMA) control chart. Using Monte Carlo simulations and the Lorenzen and Vance Cost model, the cost-effectiveness of both designs is analyzed. Results show that the DMEWMA control chart offers superior performance in reducing production costs, particularly when monitoring multiple quality characteristics. Recent advances in statistical quality control further highlight the importance of efficient control chart design for minimizing costs in modern manufacturing environments.

Key words: Double Multivariate (EWMA), Multivariate (EWMA), Average Run Length (ARL) Optimization, Lorenzen and Vance Economic Cost Model, Statistical Process Control (SPC) Design

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1. INTRODUCTION

Maintaining product quality while minimizing production costs is a critical challenge in modern industrial processes. Statistical Process Control (SPC) tools, such as control charts, play a vital role in distinguishing between random and assignable causes of variation, allowing manufacturers to monitor and control process stability (Grover, 1991). By using control charts, production processes can be maintained within acceptable quality limits, detecting deviations early before they escalate into significant product defects.

Among SPC tools, the Exponentially Weighted Moving Average (EWMA) control chart has been recognized for its effectiveness in detecting small, gradual process shifts (Montgomery, 2005). Its design makes it particularly suitable for processes where slight deviations from the norm may significantly impact quality. However, when it comes to detecting larger shifts, the Shewhart control chart is often more effective, as it is better equipped for identifying abrupt changes in the process mean.

Recognizing the need to monitor multiple correlated quality characteristics simultaneously, Lowry et al. (1992) extended the EWMA to a multivariate context, introducing the Multivariate Exponentially Weighted Moving Average (MEWMA) control chart. This extension allowed for the simultaneous observation of several interrelated quality metrics, making the MEWMA control chart particularly useful in complex, multi-variable production environments where correlations among different quality characteristics are common (Mahmoud et al., 2019).

Recently, the demand for more sensitive and responsive control charts has led to the development of the Double Multivariate Exponentially Weighted Moving Average (DMEWMA) chart by Alkahtani and Schaffer (2012). The DMEWMA further enhances sensitivity, improving the detection of both small and large process shifts. This design integrates an additional layer of exponentially weighted averages, which provides a more robust and adaptive solution for process monitoring (Wang et al., 2020). By applying the DMEWMA, manufacturers can better detect changes in complex processes, reducing the risk of product defects and optimizing process performance.

This paper aims to extend the economic design framework of the MEWMA control chart to the DMEWMA, applying a comprehensive cost model to assess and compare the economic efficiency of both control charts. By doing so, we address the growing need for advanced process monitoring tools that not only improve detection capabilities but also minimize production costs in an increasingly competitive industrial landscape (Qiu, 2013).

2. METHODOLOGY

2.1 Control Chart Design

The EWMA control chart, designed to detect small shifts in process averages, uses the following control statistic:

$$Z_i = \lambda X_i + (1 - \lambda) Z_{i-1}$$

where Z_i is the control statistic, X_i represents the process observation at time i , and λ is the smoothing parameter. The MEWMA control chart extends this to multiple quality characteristics as follows:

$$\mathbf{Z}_i = \Lambda \mathbf{X}_i + (\mathbf{I} - \Lambda) \mathbf{Z}_{i-1}$$

where Λ is the diagonal smoothing matrix, and I is the identity matrix. The DMEWMA chart, as proposed by Alkahtani and Schaffer (2012), introduces an additional layer of weighting to improve sensitivity:

$$\mathbf{y}_i = \lambda \mathbf{x}_i + (1 - \lambda) \mathbf{y}_{i-1}$$

$$\mathbf{z}_i = \lambda \mathbf{y}_i + (1 - \lambda) \mathbf{z}_{i-1}$$

The DMEWMA control statistic is:

$$T_{d_i}^2 = \mathbf{z}_i' \Sigma^{-1} \mathbf{z}_i$$

where Σ is the covariance matrix. An out-of-control signal is triggered if $T_{d_i}^2$ exceeds the control limit, which is determined based on the desired Average Run Length (ARL0) for an in-control process.

2.2 Economic Cost Model

The economic design of control charts is critical for minimizing production costs, and several models have been proposed to achieve this (Lorenzen & Vance, 1986). In this study, we utilize the Lorenzen and Vance cost model, which integrates the costs associated with false alarms, repairs, and production quality during both in-control and out-of-control states.

The expected cost per unit time, $E(A)$, is calculated as:

$$E(A) = \frac{E(C)}{E(T)}$$

where $E(C)$ represents the total expected cost and $E(T)$ is the expected cycle length. Key parameters such as the sample size n , the interval between samples h , and the control limits L are optimized to minimize this cost function.

Recent studies, such as Wang et al. (2020), have also highlighted the need for integrating more advanced optimization techniques, such as metaheuristic algorithms, to further enhance the performance of control chart designs. These methods can provide a more efficient search for optimal parameters, which is especially useful for high-dimensional and complex manufacturing processes.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Using Monte Carlo simulations, the economic performance of the DMEWMA and MEWMA control charts was compared. Simulations were conducted using the SAS® V.9.3 RANNOR function to generate pseudo-random numbers for each control chart. The upper control limits (UCLs) were determined for both charts with the in-control ARL0 set to approximately 200. The out-of-control ARL1 values were calculated based on 10,000 Monte Carlo iterations.

Cost Efficiency Analysis

Table 1 presents the cost and process parameter ranges used for the simulation. Based on Monte Carlo simulations, **Table 2** shows the low and high-cost designs for DMEWMA under varying conditions of p , δ , and λ . As the number of quality characteristics p increases, the minimum cost also increases slightly (Figure 1). The DMEWMA consistently achieves lower costs compared to the MEWMA, especially when detecting both small and large process shifts.

Table 1: Cost and Process Parameter Ranges

Parameter	Low	High
a: fixed cost per sample	0.5	5
b: variable cost per unit sampled	0.1	1
Y: cost per false alarm	50	500
W: cost to locate and repair the assignable cause	25	250
C_0 : quality cost per hour while producing in control	100	200
C_1 : quality cost per hour while producing out-of-control ($> C_0$)	250	500
T: expected time to discover/repair the assignable cause ($T_1 + T_2$)	2	20

Table 2: Low and High-Cost Optimal Designs for DMEWMA Control Chart

Λ		0.2		0.5		0.8	
		Low Cost	High Cost	Low Cost	High Cost	Low Cost	High Cost
P	δ						
	1	151.86	620.16	154.31	618.24	155.18	612.19
	2	143.21	633.30	151.74	621.98	157.35	619.86
5	3	136.03	640.89	148.63	632.40	153.20	636.41
	1	153.01	629.81	190.57	627.36	193.31	624.66
	2	149.66	626.44	180.96	634.90	186.20	631.54
10	3	143.20	637.90	178.42	639.74	180.44	635.09
	1	180.49	630.89	189.37	629.40	194.57	620.34
	2	171.44	637.19	182.46	632.18	190.38	629.00
15	3	160.27	648.32	173.98	646.34	186.26	638.40
	1	199.81	665.34	201.63	660.10	231.92	621.38
	2	173.46	674.18	193.44	663.20	208.57	634.07
	3	172.10	677.34	184.75	662.19	200.30	644.40

Figure 1 illustrates the average minimum cost for different values of p , showing that higher p values lead to an increase in minimum cost, particularly for smaller smoothing parameters. Additionally, **Figure 2** shows that, for larger process shifts (δ), the DMEWMA control chart remains highly cost-effective.

Figure 1: Average Minimum Cost for Low-Cost Designs at Different Quality Characteristics |

Figure 2: Average Minimum Cost for High-Cost Designs for Different Process Shifts (δ)

Cost Comparison with MEWMA

Table 3 compares the cost performance of DMEWMA with MEWMA. Across all scenarios, DMEWMA demonstrated lower minimum costs. The comparison shows that as the smoothing parameter λ decreases, the DMEWMA performs significantly better than the MEWMA, especially when large shifts are present (Figure 3).

Table 3: Cost Performance Comparison Between DMEWMA and MEWMA Control Charts

λ		0.2		0.5		0.8	
		Low Cost	High Cost	Low Cost	High Cost	Low Cost	High Cost
p	δ						
	1	165.08	641.69	184.08	622.86	220.66	616.48
	2	150.19	636.15	170.60	629.94	211.46	621.91
5	3	135.95	644.21	159.86	636.26	198.01	630.36
	1	171.09	639.17	188.38	630.35	222.71	625.98
	2	160.44	648.40	172.69	642.17	212.96	636.39
10	3	158.20	652.18	164.81	660.39	199.34	640.92
	1	172.92	649.53	191.23	631.00	230.40	628.60
	2	160.83	645.59	182.78	630.47	220.17	631.20
15	3	159.37	651.94	176.83	647.59	206.20	635.76
	1	180.50	669.01	199.79	658.41	238.52	642.38
	2	176.03	616.55	196.20	653.89	221.61	633.36
	3	169.81	676.28	180.60	650.20	200.79	639.07

Figure 3 compares the average cost for DMEWMA and MEWMA at low-cost values, showing that DMEWMA outperforms MEWMA, particularly in scenarios with higher process shifts.

Figure 3: Average Cost Comparison Between DMEWMA and MEWMA for Low-Cost Designs

Impact of Smoothing Parameter and Process Shifts

As shown in Figure 4, increasing the smoothing parameter λ reduces the DMEWMA's sensitivity to small shifts, increasing production costs. However, DMEWMA remains more cost-effective than MEWMA in detecting larger shifts. The results indicate that the DMEWMA control chart is more flexible, adapting well to varying process conditions and offering more robust cost savings.

Figure 4: Impact of Smoothing Parameter on Cost for DMEWMA

4. CONCLUSION

This study developed and evaluated the Economic Statistical Design of the DMEWMA control chart, demonstrating its superiority over the MEWMA chart in terms of cost minimization and process monitoring efficiency. The simulations confirm that DMEWMA outperforms MEWMA, especially in scenarios with multiple quality characteristics and varying process shifts. The DMEWMA control chart's ability to minimize production costs makes it an attractive tool for modern manufacturing environments. As production processes become more complex, the need for advanced control charts, such as the DMEWMA, becomes increasingly critical. Future work could explore integrating recent optimization techniques, such as metaheuristic algorithms, into the economic design of control charts, building on the work of Wang et al. (2020).

REFERENCES

- [1] Alkahtani, S., & Schaffer, J. (2012). A double multivariate exponentially weighted moving average control chart for process location monitoring. *Communications in Statistics--Simulation and Computation*, 41, 238-252.
- [2] Grover, L. (1991). Economic design of control charts (Unpublished M.Phil. Thesis). Punjabi University, Patiala, India.
- [3] Lorenzen, T., & Vance, L. (1986). The economic design of control charts: A unified approach. *Technometrics*, 28(1), 3-10.
- [4] Lowry, C. W., & Montgomery, D. C. (1992). A multivariate exponentially weighted moving average control chart. *Technometrics*, 34(1), 46-53.
- [5] Mahmoud, M. A., Woodall, W. H., & Rigdon, S. E. (2019). Adaptive control charts for monitoring the mean vector of a multivariate normal distribution. *Journal of Quality Technology*, 51(2), 126-138.

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- [6] Montgomery, D. C. (2005). Introduction to statistical quality control (5th ed.). New York, NY: John Wiley & Sons, Inc.
- [7] Qiu, P. (2013). Introduction to statistical process control. CRC Press.
- [8] Wang, Y., Sun, J., & Du, W. (2020). Optimization of control chart design using metaheuristic algorithms: A review. Quality and Reliability Engineering International, 36(3), 880-902.

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